

A density functional theory study of [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol complexes with Co, Ni, Cu and Zn metals

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Abstract : The optimization and IR spectra of the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol and its complexes with Co, Ni, Cu and Zn metals were determined by means of density functional theory (DFT) calculations using B3LYP formalism. The optimized geometries of complexes have tetrahedral structures. The C=N, C-O and N-H stretching frequency values were calculated to be in good agreement with experimental frequency data for ligand and its complexes with metals. All calculated frequencies are within 1.1% of the regions of experimental frequencies.

Keywords : DFT, Schiff base, transition metal complex.

Introduction

Synthesis and characterization of different transition metal complexes containing Schiff bases as ligands have been interested by many researchers due to their importance as catalysts for many reactions¹. There are many studies in literature about the chemistry of transition metal complexes of ligands consisting of oxygen, nitrogen and sulfur donor atoms due to their important properties such as the carcinostatic, antitumour, antiviral, antifungal, antibacterial activity in addition to their wide industrial applications². Furthermore, these compounds have become effective and stereospecific catalysts for oxidation, reduction and hydrolysis in the presence of oxygen and nitrogen as donor atoms in the complexes. It has been performed the synthesis and characterization of several transition metal complexes of novel Schiff bases³⁻¹². The [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol as Schiff base ligand and its complexes with Co, Ni, Cu and Zn metals have been synthesized and characterized in our previous experimental study¹³. The present study aims to examine the optimized geometrical parameters and com-

puted vibrational (IR) frequencies of the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol and its complexes with Co, Ni, Cu and Zn metals to compare with experimental data. Density functional theory (DFT) has been utilized for theoretical calculations.

Computational methods :

In present work theoretical calculations were based on DFT¹⁴ implemented in the Gaussian 09 software¹⁵. B3LYP-Hybrid formalism¹⁶⁻¹⁸ were used for calculations. Hybrid method of B3LYP was a high-quality DFT technique for theoretical calculations of organic chemistry¹⁹.

The theoretical approach of this study : The spin multiplicity (SM) of the molecule has been initially found by calculations of single point energy (SPE). SPEs have been computed for different numbers of SM for each molecule, and then the number of SM which gives the lowest energy based on SPE calculation has been adopted as the final SM number for related molecule. Then, each molecule was entirely optimized structurally via EG calculations with 6-31g(d,p) basis set. During this optimization calculation, all atoms are kept relaxed. A qualified error

which is called as spin contamination $\langle S^2 \rangle$ can be introduced in the cluster approach calculations with spin multiplicity (SM). This spin contamination value which shows where the unpaired electrons of the system are located must be negligible (less than 10%)²⁰. The spin contamination values were to be very small in this study. Vibrational frequencies were obtained for 6-31g(d,p), DGDZVP and CEP-121G basis sets via frequency calculations based on SPE by using the optimized geometry obtained by B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) method. A factor of 0.9613 was used to scale all frequency values to reproduce experimental fundamentals²¹. Mulliken atomic charges of atoms have been obtained by Mulliken population analysis²². Electronic configurations were obtained by natural bond orbital (NBO)²³ analysis. The criteria of convergence such as gradients of root-mean-square (rms) displacement, max displacement, rms force and max force in a calculation are 12×10^{-4} , 18×10^{-4} , 3×10^{-4} and 45×10^{-5} , respectively.

Results and discussion

The structures for the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol ligand and its complexes with metals have been suggested in our previous experimental study (Fig. 1)¹³. Geometries of the ligand and its complexes with metals were constructed by using these suggested structures. Initially, the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol ligand has been geometrically optimized by means of EG calculations. The equilibrium geometry of the ligand is represented in Fig. 2.

SM numbers for the ligand complexes with Zn, Cu, Ni and Co metals have been determined to be 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively. The optimized geometry of the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol complexes with Zn metal is shown in Fig. 3. The computed $\langle S^2 \rangle$ values in this optimization calculations indicated that the spin contamination was negligible, which indicates it was very small (max 2.4% after annihilation). Electron configuration of metal atoms, spin density and Mulliken charge values of the optimized complexes with Zn, Cu, Ni and Co metals are presented in Table 1. Fig. 4 represents Mulliken atomic charges with color representation for optimized ligand complexes. As can be seen from Table 1, metal atoms have a high spin density, which indicates that the unpaired electrons are localized on metal

Fig. 1. Experimentally¹³ suggested structures of (a) the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol ligand and (b) its complexes with metal atoms (where M = Co, Ni, Cu and Zn).

Fig. 2. Optimized geometry of ligand : (a) top view and (b) side view.

Fig. 3. Optimized geometry of complex with Zn : (a) top view and (b) side views.

Table 1. Mulliken charge and spin density values and electron configuration of metal atoms of the optimized complexes with Zn, Cu, Ni and Co metals

Complex	Mulliken charge	Mulliken spin density	Electron configuration
Zn	0.951	-	[core]4S(0.36)3d(9.91) 4p(0.42)5p(0.01)
Cu	0.851	0.678	[core]4S(0.31) 3d(9.16)4p(0.39)
Ni	0.939	1.711	[core]4S(0.30) 3d(8.15)4p(0.38)
Co	0.998	2.779	[core]4S(0.26) 3d(7.17)4p(0.38)

atoms. The optimized geometries of the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol complexes with Zn, Cu, Ni and Co metals have similar tetrahedral structure (Fig. 4). In detail, optimized complexes with Cu, Ni and Co atoms have distorted tetrahedral structures while

the complex with Zn atom has a normal tetrahedral structure. The reason of this might be that spin density values of metal atoms in the optimized complexes with Cu, Ni and Co atoms have spin density whereas there is no spin density for Zn atom in the optimized complexes with Zn. Furthermore, according to Fig. 4 the atomic charges of metal atoms for the complexes are higher than those of the other atoms of the ligands, showing highest positive character on metal atoms.

The vibrational frequency values calculated with B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) (N-H, C-O and C=N stretching frequencies) for the optimized complexes are tabulated in Table 2 which also shows experimental data. As seen from Table, the calculated values of C=N, C-O and N-H stretching frequencies are in well agreement with experimental frequency data¹³ for the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol ligand and its complexes with Zn, Cu, Ni and Co metals. C=N stretching

Fig. 4. Mulliken atomic charges with color representation for optimized complexes : (a) Zn-complex, (b) Ni-complex, (c) Cu-complex, (d) Co-complex and (e) color scale for charges (left side : lowest charge (-) and right side : highest charge (+)).

frequencies for ligand and its complexes with metals (Zn, Cu, Ni and Co) were calculated to be 1623, 1618, 1618, 1617 and 1616 cm^{-1} , respectively. Experimental frequencies were reported as 1606, 1601, 1600, 1596 and 1598 cm^{-1} , respectively. The stretching frequencies of C-O mode were computed as 1262, 1250, 1248, 1252 and 1250 cm^{-1} for ligand and its complexes with Zn, Cu, Ni and Co metals, respectively. Corresponding experimental frequency values were respectively 1265, 1257, 1260, 1258 and 1257 cm^{-1} . N-H stretching frequencies are also in corresponding experimental frequency ranges. Additionally, it can be also concluded that in experimental frequency region for N-H mode there are symmetrical and anti-symmetrical stretching frequencies. In addition, these stretching frequency values are similar with the experimentally observed frequencies for similar compounds^{9,10}. Moreover, Table 2 depicts the C=C stretching regions of the benzene rings in ligand and its complexes. The calculated C=C stretching regions of the benzene rings match well with the experimental C=C stretching region

(1.680 and 1.580 cm^{-1})²⁴. All calculated frequencies based on B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) method are within 1.1% of the regions of experimental frequencies, which is a reasonable error as pointed out in reference²⁵. Table 3 represents a comparison between the vibrational frequency values for structures obtained by using 6-31g(d,p), DGDZVP and CEP-121G basis sets. As can be seen from Table 3, vibrational frequencies obtained by these basis sets are relatively similar.

Conclusions

DFT calculations with B3LYP method have been performed on the optimization and vibrational IR spectra of the [(4-aminophenyl)imino]methyl-6-methoxy-4-nitrophenol and its complexes with Co, Ni, Cu and Zn metals. The optimized geometries of complexes have a tetrahedral structure. The calculated stretching frequency values of C=N, C-O and N-H match well with experimental frequency data for the ligand and its complexes with Zn, Cu, Ni and Co metals. All calculated frequen-

Table 2. The theoretical and experimental vibrational frequency values (cm^{-1}) for the optimized geometries of ligand and its complexes^a

Frequency types	Ligand		Complex with Zn		Complex with Cu		Complex with Ni		Complex with Co	
	Theoretical	Experimental	Theoretical	Experimental	Theoretical	Experimental	Theoretical	Experimental	Theoretical	Experimental
C=N stretching	15C=14N 48C=47N	1623 1606	1618 1616	1601	1618 1615	1600	1617 1615	1596	1616 1615	1598
C-O stretching	16C-27O 49C-60O	1262 1265	1250 1251	1257	1248 1253	1260	1252 1253	1258	1250 1251	1257
N-H symmetrical stretching	11N-(12H,13H) 44N-(45H,46H)	3443 3390-3325	3441 3444	3446	3440 3442	3543-3447	3441 3445	3682-2900	3441 3444	3400-3100
N-H anti-symmetrical stretching	11N-(12H,13H) 44N-(45H,46H)	3549	3546 3550		3544 3547		3545 3551		3545 3550	
C=C stretching of benzene rings		1583-1556	1593-1526		1592-1525		1592-1526		1593-1525	

^aAll theoretical values were obtained by using B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) method in this study and experimental values are taken from a study of Bakirdere *et al.*¹³.

Table 3. The calculated theoretical vibrational frequency values (cm^{-1}) for the optimized geometries of ligand and its complexes

Frequency types	Ligand		Complex with Zn		Complex with Cu		Complex with Ni		Complex with Co	
	Basis set	Basis set	Basis set	Basis set	Basis set	Basis set	Basis set	Basis set	Basis set	Basis set
C=N stretching	6-31g(d,p) 15C=14N 48C=47N	DGDZVP 1627 1627	CEP-121G 1618 1616	CEP-121G 1622 1617	DGDZVP 1618 1615	CEP-121G 1614 1621	DGDZVP 1617 1615	CEP-121G 1613 1612	DGDZVP 1616 1615	CEP-121G 1614 1612
C-O stretching	6-31g(d,p) 16C-27O 49C-60O	DGDZVP 1308 3445	CEP-121G 1250 1251	CEP-121G 1304 1305	DGDZVP 1248 1253	CEP-121G 1303 1305	DGDZVP 1252 1253	CEP-121G 1306 1307	DGDZVP 1250 1251	CEP-121G 1304 1305
N-H symmetrical stretching	6-31g(d,p) 11N-(12H,13H) 44N-(45H,46H)	DGDZVP 3452 3444	CEP-121G 3441 3444	CEP-121G 3443 3446	DGDZVP 3440 3442	CEP-121G 3442 3444	DGDZVP 3441 3445	CEP-121G 3442 3446	DGDZVP 3441 3444	CEP-121G 3449 3445
N-H anti-symmetrical stretching	6-31g(d,p) 11N-(12H,13H) 44N-(45H,46H)	DGDZVP 3560 3561	CEP-121G 3546 3550	CEP-121G 3557 3561	DGDZVP 3544 3547	CEP-121G 3555 3558	DGDZVP 3545 3551	CEP-121G 3556 3562	DGDZVP 3545 3550	CEP-121G 3557 3561
C=C stretching of benzene rings		1583- 1556	1593- 1526		1592- 1525		1592- 1526		1593- 1525	

cies are within 1.1% of the regions of experimental frequencies.

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